

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION IN SOCIETY

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Abstract: This article is the current era, when societies are actively integrating with each other, the development of information technology, communication, technologies is becoming globalized, in a word, the era of globalization and information societies are settling down, and it is increasingly vital for us to study it comprehensively in the period when the settlement of the information society is accelerating. is becoming a necessity, and the study of the history and causes of the origin of such a society is one of the main issues on the agenda.

Key words: technology, information technology, integrating, information, communication, globalization, virtual services.

Today's period is the period when societies are actively integrating with each other, the development of information technology, communication, and technologies is becoming globalized. In the period when the establishment of the information society is accelerating, it is becoming more and more vital for us to study it in every way, and to study the history and reasons of the origin of such a society is one of the main issues on the agenda, because today we are gradually moving towards this society. From the beginning of the human race to the present century, it has passed through various development paths and received the name of civilization. From the most primitive period of the development period to the present advanced period, information has become important in determining the regulatory task of mankind.

The appropriate use of information from media sources and other suppliers depends on an individual's professional analysis of information needs, as well as information seeking and evaluation. The term "information" has many definitions. It can mean information, knowledge gained through research, experience or learning, as well as signals or signs. Simply put, information is information that has been collected, processed, and interpreted in a user-friendly form. Another different definition of information is "knowledge presented in an easy-to-understand form." In Latin, "informatio" means explanation, statement. In the past, behind this concept was understood the information given by people to each other orally, in writing and in other ways. The definition of information in a broad sense is given in the science of cybernetics. According to its founder Norbert Wiener, "information is a description of

content from the outside world, which we adapt to it and it to our senses."

The need for information is the need to obtain information necessary for the performance of certain social roles and tasks. In most cases, the consumer understands what he needs to know to achieve this or that goal and focuses his search on a certain result. For example, in the conditions of inflation, every citizen is interested in price growth. The applicant learns all the information about the rules of admission to the higher education institution. Entrepreneurs and financiers are primarily interested in the price quotation on the stock exchange. The purpose of turning to one or another information channel is clear to a person. The choice depends on the completeness of the message, the credibility or interest of the source, etc. based on But even here, the reliability of the source should be studied in depth. For example, recommendations for new literature by a person who introduces himself as a literary critic may be given for a specific purpose. So, on the basis of sorting information, its value lies to the consumer, even if he does not understand it. When evaluating a source of information, it is necessary to first determine the purpose for which a person receives information from it. This process helps identify reliable sources of information. For example, it is permissible to try to find answers to the following questions: in this case, which source is the most reliable for obtaining information? Which sources can be truthful and unbiased?

There is no reason to expect drastic changes in social structures after the transition to the information society. This structure balances the pros and cons. The stratification of people into the rich and the poor will remain almost the same, because the measure of the use of the fruits of labor will be different. Despite the differentiation of the sphere of virtual services, there will be more important (more expensive) and fewer services according to the capabilities of each member of the new society. ladi This is definitely not a positive thing. And the shortcomings of the modern information society do not end there.

The problems are related to data, such as space, that are not specific to a single country, but to several or to the whole of humanity. Banks of information on various sectors of agriculture and industry, buying potential and potential sellers are confidential secrets that belong to stock exchanges and other brokerage companies that deal with the redistribution of goods, and their constitutes wealth. But, first of all, the person in the information society suffers. Here the pros and cons are not balanced. But this is a topic for a separate article, because the avalanche of virtual information has already blown away many.

Free access to any information other than personal and corporate is good. But the bad thing is that, along with the necessary and useful information, we are bombarded with an unnecessary, often immoral stream, imposed on a person from childhood. The positives and negatives of the information society are summarized as freedom of unnecessary access with the side effect of damaging morale.

A wonderful industry of entertainment, recreation, sports, tourism has been created, people can relax, escape from work, relax, recharge their spiritual energy, and this is also about positive aspects. The negative side is the lack of demand for mental capacity due to the simplification of human needs through communication, so most often choose to watch TV programs or play computer games from the richest arsenal of services. But just as often, that choice comes down to financial payoff. If anything, that's the truth.

Characteristic features of the information society, their positive and negative aspects are clearly visible in the influence of mass media among the young generation. Forming aesthetic taste (moving) stereotypes, music, fashion for clothes are being popularized. Examples of advantages of patriotism, spirituality, and family lifestyle are given. Side-by-side, if not together, often promote non-conventional "stars" for "country" and other Christian worlds, promoting heroes who defy standards of existence.

Specific features of the information society, its pluses and minuses. It's an opportunity for creativity and laziness when it's like compensation for the unfinished act of creation in the form of cruel spectacles and watching rather than living, brought up by the media in people. Sex and drugs are often chosen over creativity - anything is more accessible. The limitless communication possibilities are great: in addition to acquaintances at work or school, "friends" appear on blogs all over the world. Minus - frequent cases of fraud, communication on an immoral basis, all this hardens and corrupts young people.

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